

On a New 3D Generalized Hunter–Saxton Equation

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The problem of integrability is studied for a 3D generalized Hunter–Saxton equation introduced recently by O.I. Morozov. A transformation is found which brings the equation into a constant-characteristic form and simultaneously trivializes the equation’s Lax representation. The transformed equation is shown to fail the Painlevé test for integrability.

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1. Introduction

In this paper, we study the three-dimensional nonlinear wave equation

$$u_{xt} = uu_{xx} - u_x^2 + u_y \quad (1)$$

introduced recently in [1] and called the 3D generalized Hunter–Saxton equation there. This equation is considered as integrable in [1] because it is associated with an infinite-dimensional Lie algebra which generates the over-determined linear problem

$$r_t = ur_x, \quad r_y = u_x r_x \quad (2)$$

called the Lax representation of (1). Note that we have corrected the sign of the last term in (1) because the equation with $-u_y$ as given in [1] would not match the linear problem (2).

The reduction of (1) with $u_y = 0$ is the equation $u_{xt} = uu_{xx} - u_x^2$ (not the Hunter–Saxton equation [2] $u_{xt} = uu_{xx} + \frac{1}{2}u_x^2$) which belongs to the Calogero’s class of exactly solvable by quadratures equations [3] $u_{xt} = uu_{xx} + F(u_x)$ with any function F . The existence of this exactly solvable two-dimensional reduction is an interesting feature but it tells nothing about the integrability of the three-dimensional equation (1) itself. It also remains unknown what

the parameterless first-order scalar linear problem (2) means and how it can be used to integrate the nonlinear equation (1). In our experience, statements about the integrability of nonlinear equations associated with infinite-dimensional Lie algebras should be considered with caution [4, 5]. Definitely, the integrability of (1) deserves further investigation.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we find a transformation which relates the nonlinear equation (1) with a simpler equation possessing constant characteristics and simultaneously makes the Lax representation (2) trivial. In Section 3, we carry out the singularity analysis of the nonlinear equation obtained via the transformation and show that the equation fails the Painlevé test for integrability. Section 4 contains concluding remarks.

2. Transformation

To transform the nonlinear equation (1) into a simpler equation with constant characteristics, we follow the way successfully used in [6–10] for a series of other nonlinear equations. However, now we do it for the first time with a three-dimensional equation.

The change of variables

$$\begin{aligned} x &= w(z, y, t), \\ u(w(z, y, t), y, t) &= v(z, y, t), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

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made in (1), leads us to

$$v_{zt} - \frac{w_t + v}{w_z} v_{zz} + \frac{v_z^2}{w_z} - w_z v_y + \left(\frac{w_t + v}{w_z^2} w_{zz} - \frac{w_{zt}}{w_z} + w_y \right) v_z = 0, \quad (4)$$

where $w(z, y, t)$ is arbitrary (with $w_z \neq 0$, of course). We see that the choice of $w : w_t = -v$ would eliminate the term with v_{zz} and simplify (4) as

$$v_{zt} + 2 \frac{v_z^2}{w_z} - w_z v_y + w_y v_z = 0. \quad (5)$$

Therefore we make the substitution

$$v = -w_t \quad (6)$$

in (4) (or, equivalently, in (5)), multiply the result by $-1/w_z^2$, and get

$$\partial_t \left(\frac{w_{zt}}{w_z^2} - \frac{w_y}{w_z} \right) = 0, \quad (7)$$

which is integrated as

$$\frac{w_{zt}}{w_z^2} - \frac{w_y}{w_z} = h(z, y), \quad (8)$$

where $h(z, y)$ is arbitrary.

Without loss of generality, we can choose $h(z, y) = 0$ in (8), for the following reason. The relations (3), $x = w(z, y, t)$ and $u = v(z, y, t)$, can be considered as a parametric representation of solutions $u(x, y, t)$ of (1), where z serves as the parameter and the arbitrariness of $w(z, y, t)$ corresponds to the arbitrariness of the parameter's choice, $z \mapsto f(z, y, t)$ with arbitrary $f(z, y, t)$. When we choose $w(z, y, t)$ to satisfy (6), there still remains the arbitrariness $z \mapsto g(z, y)$ of the parameter's choice, with arbitrary $g(z, y)$. This change of z , $z \mapsto g(z, y)$, generates the change of $h(z, y)$ in (8), $h(z, y) \mapsto g_y + h(z, y)g_z$, therefore we can always make $h = 0$ in (8) by an appropriate choice of the parameter z . Moreover, even when we fix $h = 0$ in (8), there still remains the arbitrariness $z \mapsto a(z)$ of the parameter's choice, with arbitrary $a(z)$.

Consequently, all solutions $u(x, y, t)$ of the nonlinear equation (1) are parametrically represented by all solutions $w(z, y, t)$ (with $w_z \neq 0$) of the nonlinear equation

$$w_{zt} = w_z w_y \quad (9)$$

via the relations

$$\begin{aligned} x &= w(z, y, t), \\ u(x, y, t) &= -\partial_t w(z, y, t), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where z serves as the parameter. The arbitrariness $z \mapsto a(z)$ of the parameter's choice, with any $a(z)$, corresponds to the invariance of (9) and has no effect on solutions of (1). Of course, all our consideration was purely local.

It is interesting to see how the transformation (10), relating (1) with (9), acts on the (so-called) Lax representation (2). We introduce the function $s(z, y, t)$, such that

$$r(w(z, y, t), y, t) = s(z, y, t), \quad (11)$$

and obtain from (2), (10) and (9) the trivial linear system

$$s_t = 0, \quad s_y = 0. \quad (12)$$

Since $s = s(z)$ follows from (12), the linear system (2) may be somehow related to the transformation (10) we found, but it definitely tells nothing about how to integrate the nonlinear equations (1) and (9).

3. Singularity analysis

We have never seen the nonlinear equation (9) in the literature. Let us study its integrability by the Painlevé test for partial differential equations [11, 12]. In our experience, based on the singularity analysis of wide classes of nonlinear systems [13–16], the Painlevé test is a reliable and convenient tool, capable not only to detect all known integrable cases but also to discover some interesting new ones [17–19].

A hypersurface $\phi(z, y, t) = 0$ is non-characteristic for (9) if $\phi_z \phi_t \neq 0$. Near a non-characteristic hypersurface $\phi = 0$, the dominant singular behavior of solutions w of the nonlinear equation (9) is

$$w = -\frac{\phi_t}{\phi_y} \log \phi + \dots \quad (13)$$

Note that (13) does not work if $\phi_y = 0$ (perhaps because (9) with $w_y = 0$ is the linear equation $w_{zt} = 0$ whose solutions have singularities at the characteristics only). In what follows, we consider the generic case with $\phi_y \neq 0$, and we set $\phi_y = 1$ without loss of generality,

$$\phi = y + \psi(z, t), \quad \psi_z \psi_t \neq 0. \quad (14)$$

This dominant logarithmic singularity (13) is not a good starting point for the Painlevé analysis. The situation, however, can be improved by the new dependent variable $q(z, y, t)$,

$$q = w_z, \quad (15)$$

which turns the nonlinear equation (9) into

$$qq_{zt} - q_z q_t - q^2 q_y = 0. \quad (16)$$

Near a hypersurface $\phi = 0$ with ϕ given by (14), the dominant singular behavior of solutions q of the nonlinear equation (16) is

$$q = -\psi_z \psi_t \phi^{-1} + \dots \quad (17)$$

Now we can try to represent the general solution of (16) near $\phi = 0$ by the generalized Laurent series

$$q = q_0(z, t)\phi^{-1} + \dots + q_i(z, t)\phi^{i-1} + \dots, \quad (18)$$

where ϕ is given by (14). We substitute the expansion (18) to the nonlinear equation (16), collect terms with ϕ^{n-4} , separately for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, and obtain in this way the following. The resonances, where arbitrary functions can enter the expansion (18), turn out to be

$$n = -1, 1, \quad (19)$$

and $n = -1$, as always, corresponds to the arbitrariness of $\psi(z, t)$ in ϕ (14). At $n = 0$, we get

$$q_0 = -\psi_z \psi_t, \quad (20)$$

as expected due to (17). However, at $n = 1$, where we have the resonance and the function $q_1(z, t)$ remains undetermined (arbitrary), we get the nontrivial compatibility condition

$$\psi_{zt} = 0, \quad (21)$$

which shows that the expansion (18) is valid only for a quite restricted class of hypersurfaces $\phi = 0$. Consequently, the nonlinear equation (16) has failed the Painlevé test for integrability.

It is interesting to see what is the valid expansion for the general solution of the nonlinear equation (16). To avoid the appearance of the nontrivial compatibility condition (21), we have to modify the expansion (18) by a logarithmic term introduced before the resonance term,

$$q = q_0(z, t)\phi^{-1} + b(z, t) \log \phi + q_1(z, t) + \dots \quad (22)$$

It follows from (16) and (22) that q_0 is given by (20),

$$b = -\frac{1}{2}\psi_{zt}, \quad (23)$$

and $q_1(z, t)$ remains arbitrary. All the higher-order terms of the expansion (22) are determined by (16) recursively, in terms of two arbitrary functions, $\psi(z, t)$ and $q_1(z, t)$, and their derivatives. For example, the next three terms of the expansion (22) are

$$c(z, t)(\log \phi)^2 \phi + d(z, t)(\log \phi) \phi + q_2(z, t)\phi, \quad (24)$$

where

$$c = -\frac{\psi_{zt}^2}{12\psi_z \psi_t}, \quad (25)$$

but we omit the expressions for d and q_2 as cumbersome and unnecessary. We have got a so-called logarithmic psi-series [12]. Such expansions are typical for nonlinear equation considered as non-integrable (at least, currently).

4. Conclusion

Summarizing the obtained results, we can state that the 3D generalized Hunter–Saxton

equation is most probably non-integrable. We also believe that it may be more convenient and productive to further investigate this equation in its equivalent form $w_{zt} = w_z w_y$ we found.

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